

1 Triple oxygen isotope fractionation between CaCO₃ and H₂O in
2 inorganically precipitated calcite and aragonite

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13 **Highlights:**

14 The ^{17}O fractionation between CaCO_3 and its parent water is examined experimentally

15 The triple oxygen isotope fractionation slope, $(\ln^{17}\alpha/\ln^{18}\alpha)$, is similar in calcite and aragonite

16 The fractionation slope is independent of temperature at 10, 27°C but somewhat lower at

17 35°C

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21 **ABSTRACT**

22 Carbonate bearing materials, such as foraminifera, mollusks shells, or speleothems, have
23 the potential to preserve geochemical and isotopic signatures reflecting the environmental
24 conditions at the time they formed. Beyond the conventional $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, information from triple oxygen
25 isotopes (reported as $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$, which is defined as $(\ln(\delta^{17}\text{O}/1000+1) - \lambda_{\text{ref}} \ln(\delta^{18}\text{O}/1000+1)) \times 10^6$)
26 in these archives promises to be a valuable tool to reconstruct past hydrological processes. The
27 goal of this study is to determine the triple oxygen isotope fractionation between CaCO_3 and H_2O
28 under well-constrained laboratory conditions. We performed laboratory experiments to precipitate
29 CaCO_3 polymorphs, either calcite or aragonite, at temperatures between 10 and 35°C. We then
30 evaluated the effect of polymorphism, temperature, and solution concentration on the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of
31 CO_2 extracted from these carbonates and the ^{17}O isotopic fractionation ($^{17}\alpha$) between water and
32 CaCO_3 . The obtained values of $^{18}\alpha$ and $^{17}\alpha$ between CO_2 extracted from CaCO_3 and parent water
33 allow us to calculate the fractionation slope $\theta (= \ln^{17}\alpha / \ln^{18}\alpha)$. Our observations suggest that θ is
34 indistinguishable at temperatures of 10 and 27°C, but is slightly lower at 35°C. The lower value at
35 35°C may be related to dis-equilibrium during these experiments. We found that θ is independent
36 of polymorph and of solution concentration, indicating that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is less sensitive than $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ to
37 these geochemical parameters and can thus be a robust proxy for reconstructing $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of parent
38 water.

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40 **Keywords: Triple oxygen isotope fractionation; Calcite–Aragonite; $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$; Paleo-**
41 **hydrology proxy.**

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43 1. INTRODUCTION

44 Calcium carbonate is well-known to have the potential to preserve various geochemical
45 signals, reflecting the environmental conditions at the time in which the carbonate mineral formed.
46 Since the pioneering works of Urey (1947) and Emiliani (1966), the isotopic composition,
47 specifically $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, of marine and terrestrial carbonates has been used as a paleoclimate proxy that
48 records a combination of temperature and water isotopic composition. Additional carbonate-based
49 proxies, such as Mg/Ca and clumped isotopes, are often used as geochemical thermometers (e.g.,
50 Eiler, 2011; Elderfield et al., 2006), complementing information from $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. In terrestrial
51 carbonates, such as speleothems, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is interpreted as a recorder of the weighted mean rainfall
52 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, often reflecting the amount of rainfall in low latitude records (e.g., McDermott, 2004). This,
53 however, does not capture the full hydrological complexity, such as the variability in moisture
54 sources and the effect of local evaporation (although a few studies were able to link speleothem
55 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ changes with changes in moisture sources during specific time intervals in the past, such as
56 the 8.2 ka event; e.g., Dominguez-Villar et al., 2009; Voarintsoa et al., 2019). These gaps can be
57 filled by information from $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in water that may be archived in a variety of carbonates.

58 The parameter $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is expressed as $(\ln(\delta^{17}\text{O}/1000+1) - \lambda_{\text{ref}} \ln(\delta^{18}\text{O}/1000+1)) \times 10^6$, or
59 simply $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}} = (\delta^{17}\text{O} - \lambda_{\text{ref}} \times \delta^{18}\text{O}) \times 10^3$, and is reported in per meg (e.g., Barkan and Luz, 2012;
60 Luz and Barkan, 2010). The slope λ_{ref} is a mass dependent reference, with the value 0.528 used in
61 water, CO_2 , and CaCO_3 .

62 Meteoric water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is largely dependent on the atmospheric conditions, such as relative
63 humidity, in the region where water vapor form (e.g., Angert et al., 2004; Luz and Barkan, 2010).
64 However, there are indications for the influence of additional processes during precipitation,
65 associated with local conditions. The $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ data of Li et al. (2015) from U.S tap waters suggest

66 a potential influence of mixing of moisture sources and re-evaporation during precipitation. In high
67 latitude regions, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is mainly influenced by kinetic processes related to super-saturation
68 during vapor condensation at cold climate (e.g. Landais et al., 2012; Schoenemann et al., 2014).
69 In mid to low latitude regions, $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ is mainly affected by evaporation of rain droplets,
70 especially during warm climatic conditions (Landais et al., 2010; Risi et al., 2013; Li et al., 2015;
71 Passey and Ji, 2019).

72 Whereas fossil water $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ can be obtained from ice cores, fluid inclusions, or gypsum
73 hydration water (Affolter et al., 2015; Gázquez et al., 2018; Landais et al., 2008), these archives
74 are limited in their geographical distribution. A broader coverage can be obtained by measuring
75 $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in carbonates. Recent analytical developments (Passey et al., 2014; Barkan et al., 2015;
76 Mahata et al., 2016) enable high precision measurements of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in CO_2 released from CaCO_3 ,
77 which in turn may serve as a recorder of $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of the water in which the mineral grows (Passey
78 et al., 2014; Levin et al., 2014; Passey and Ji, 2019). Despite the recent advancement in measuring
79 triple oxygen isotopes in carbonate materials, the fractionation involved in this proxy has not yet
80 been characterized by laboratory experiments, to provide a framework necessary to quantitatively
81 interpret past records. Here, we examine the triple oxygen isotope fractionation in the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$
82 system focusing on the effect of mineralogy, using laboratory precipitation experiments of calcite,
83 aragonite, and their mixtures at temperatures of 10, 27, and 35°C. We also examine the role of
84 initial solution concentrations, as a simple way to assess the role of dissolved inorganic carbon
85 (DIC) concentration on the triple oxygen isotope fractionation in the same system. The data allows
86 us to calculate the fractionation slope, $\theta (= \ln^{17}\alpha / \ln^{18}\alpha)$, in order to interpret $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in natural
87 carbonates as a geochemical archive for paleo-hydrological processes.

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2. METHODS

2.1. Precipitation experiment

92 Precipitation experiments were performed by mixing solutions containing NaHCO₃ (Baker
93 Analyzed Reagent, J.T. Baker ref. 1-3506) and CaCl₂·2H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich CAS no. 10035-04-
94 8) to reach an initial DIC concentration of 25 mM (at 10, 27, and 35°C) and 5mM (at 27°C, to test
95 the effect of initial DIC). MgCl₂·6H₂O (Sigma Aldrich CAS no. 7791-18-6) was added to obtain
96 a total Mg–Ca concentration of 25mM or 5mM, respectively. The Mg:Ca ratio for either the 5mM
97 or 25mM solution was defined following Morse et al. (1997), which we used as a guide for the
98 Mg:Ca–Temperature combination to precipitate either calcite, aragonite, or a mixture of both
99 (Table 1, Figure 1). It varied between 0 and 5. The composition of CO₂ extracted from the NaHCO₃
100 is 26.88 ‰ versus VSMOW for δ¹⁸O and -260 per meg for ¹⁷O_{excess}. All samples were prepared
101 without initial CO₂ bubbling. Starting (pre-mixing) solutions were allowed to reach isotopic
102 equilibrium at room temperature overnight (>15 h), so that the starting solution is the same in all
103 experiments. This equilibration time was based on estimated equilibration times of Beck et al.
104 (2005) and Affek (2013) for δ¹⁸O and Δ₄₇. We assume that δ¹⁷O would have a similar equilibration
105 time. This assumption is consistent with model simulations of Guo and Zhou (2019), where the
106 time to reach equilibrium is similar for δ¹⁸O and δ¹⁷O. This model predicts that isotopic exchange
107 between dissolved inorganic carbon and water should reach equilibrium after about 20 hours at
108 pH=10.4 and 25°C; equilibration at the lower pH of our experiments is expected to be faster. The
109 solutions were then thermally equilibrated at their corresponding experimental temperature for at
110 least 1 hour prior to mixing (following Kim and O'Neil., 1997). A 200 ml aliquot of the solution
111 mixture was placed in a 250 ml Erlenmeyer flask that was covered with two layers of Parafilm and

112 a glass plate. The pH of the starting and ending solution varied between 5.85 and 7.67, indicating
113 a HCO_3^- dominated solution (Table 1).

114 CaCO_3 precipitation occurred via passive CO_2 degassing. Experiments were performed at 10,
115 27, and 35°C. Temperature was maintained by placing the precipitating solutions in an incubator
116 (10°C) or in a circulating water bath (27 and 35°C). The time of appearance of the first precipitates
117 varied depending on the temperature and on the initial solution concentration. In the 35°C
118 experiments, precipitates were observed 15-30 minutes after mixing the solutions, and the
119 experiment lasted ~3 days. In the 27°C experiment, precipitates were observed after few hours at
120 25mM or after ~24hrs at 5mM, and the precipitation experiment lasted ~7 days and ~29 days for
121 the 25 mM and 5 mM, respectively. In the 10°C experiment, the appearance of first precipitates
122 took 1–2 days, and the precipitation experiment lasted ~50 days. We note that the ending date for
123 each experiment was determined by assessing when no more precipitates were being produced.

124 Water evaporation during the experiment was negligible, as seen by the lack of change in
125 solution volume through the experiment and by the similar $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the water at the
126 beginning and at the end of the experiment. The mineralogical composition and proportion of
127 calcite and aragonite in the CaCO_3 precipitates was determined by X-ray diffractometer (Bruker
128 AXS D8 Advance at the Harvey M. Krueger Family Center for Nanoscience and Nanotechnology
129 at The Hebrew University of Jerusalem).

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131 **2.2. Analytical procedures and isotopic measurements**

132 The analytical procedures for determining the triple oxygen isotope composition in
133 carbonates and water were previously described by Barkan et al. (2015; 2019) and Affek and
134 Barkan (2018), respectively. Briefly, CaCO_3 samples were digested by phosphoric acid at 25°C

135 following McCrea (1950), and water samples were equilibrated with CO₂ following the technique
136 of Epstein and Mayeda (1953) and O'Neil and Truesdell (1991). In both cases, the resulting CO₂
137 underwent isotopic exchange over hot platinum with pure O₂ of known isotopic composition,
138 followed by O₂ being analyzed for δ¹⁷O and δ¹⁸O values. The O₂ samples were measured by dual-
139 inlet mass spectrometry versus an O₂ working reference gas that was calibrated with respect to
140 VSMOW. Each sample was analyzed in duplicates or triplicates. All measurements were
141 performed alongside an in-house CO₂ standard that was analyzed daily to check the performance
142 of the CO₂-O₂ isotope exchange line and the mass spectrometer. The typical reproducibility of
143 ¹⁷O_{excess} is approximately ±6 per meg (Barkan et al., 2019).

144

145 **3. RESULTS**

146 The results from this study are presented in Figures 1–4, and details are given in Tables 1–
147 3.

148

149 **3.1. Mineralogy and molarity**

150 Figure 1 depicts the distribution of the carbonate mineralogy as a function of temperature
151 and the Mg:Ca ratio of the starting solution. The results are in good agreement with the
152 mineralogical distribution obtained by Morse et al. (1997) and Balthasar and Cusack (2015).
153 Briefly, in the absence of magnesium (Mg:Ca=0) the dominant calcium carbonate phase is calcite.
154 At higher Mg:Ca ratios or high temperatures, aragonite is the dominant phase.

155 Our results show that in precipitation temperatures between 10 and 35°C, ¹⁷O_{excess} is
156 independent of mineralogy and of the molarity of the starting solution (Table 2). Values of ¹⁷O_{excess}
157 of CO₂ extracted from carbonate (denoted CO_{2-carb}) overlap between calcite (–185 to –202 per
158 meg) and aragonite (–185 to –215 per meg). The mean difference in ¹⁷O_{excess} between water and

159 $\text{CO}_{2\text{-carb}}$ is 215 ± 17 (1SD) per meg for samples that are mostly calcite and 220 ± 12 per meg for
 160 samples that are mostly aragonite. When considering the molarity of the starting solution, the
 161 difference in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ between $\text{CO}_{2\text{-carb}}$ and water is 204 ± 16 (1SD) per meg for the 5mM
 162 experiments and 212 ± 4 per meg for the 25mM experiments at 27°C .
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164
 165 **Figure 1:** Scatter plot showing the distribution of CaCO_3 polymorphs precipitated in this study, as
 166 a function of Mg:Ca ratio and temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$), compared to the data of Morse et al. (1997). The
 167 proportion of each mineral in each sample was determined via XRD, and is depicted in the blue /
 168 green partitioning of the symbol. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend,
 169 the reader is referred to the web version of this article).
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171
 172 **3.2. ^{18}O fractionation factors**

173 Table 1 summarizes the experimental conditions and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data for carbonates and their
 174 parent water, along with the resulting ^{18}O fractionation factors ($^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$). The expected
 175 difference of ~ 0.8 ‰ (e.g., Kim et al., 2007b) between calcite and aragonite is observed in our
 176 5mM experiments. At 25mM, no significant difference is observed between the two polymorphs.
 177 The reason for this may be related to kinetic isotopic fractionation that is often observed in

178 laboratory precipitation. The precipitation rates are significantly higher at 25mM relative to 5mM
179 (calculated using kinetic parameters for calcite and aragonite precipitation from Burton and Walter
180 (1987) with saturation state (Ω) calculated from the concentrations at the beginning of our
181 experiments and the solubility product of calcite or aragonite from Mucci (1983), and compared
182 at 27°C). The higher concentration experiments are therefore more sensitive to kinetic isotope
183 effects, that may affect the difference in $^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ between the two polymorphs. Burton and
184 Walter (1987) observed higher precipitation rates in aragonite relative to calcite when compared
185 at the same saturation state (at relatively low Ω , $\log(\Omega-1) < 1$). In our experiments Ω is significantly
186 higher, but is lower for aragonite ($\log(\Omega-1)=4.2-4.7$) than for calcite ($\log(\Omega-1)=5.2-5.3$) due to
187 aragonite being more soluble, leading to faster precipitation in the calcite experiments. Therefore,
188 a combination of kinetic isotope effects would likely influence $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of calcite and aragonite to a
189 different extent, and may thus affect the difference between them.

190 Figure 2 shows the ^{18}O fractionation curve between CaCO_3 and H_2O determined from our
191 experimental study, in comparison to previous studies, including biogenic carbonates and
192 laboratory precipitation of both calcite and aragonite. The fractionation curve for all our 25mM
193 samples precipitated at 10, 27, and 35°C, is expressed as $1000\ln^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}} = 17.743 \pm 0.493 * 1000/T - 30.316 \pm 1.675$ (with T in degrees K). It is higher than the aragonite fractionation curve
194 of Kim et al. (2007b) and Patterson et al. (1993), slightly lower than the biogenic aragonite
195 fractionation curve of Grossman and Ku (1986), and is similar to the curve from slowly grown
196 calcite of Gabitov et al. (2012). Despite the wide range of the $^{18}\alpha$ fractionation curves (Figure 2)
197 and the potential kinetic effects associated with this range, the overall consistency of our $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
198 data with these expected fractionation factors suggest that our ^{17}O fractionation factors are broadly
199 relevant for calcite and aragonite of both biogenic and abiogenic sources.
200

201

202 **Figure 2:** The $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ isotopic fractionation curve between CaCO_3 and H_2O calculated in this
 203 study (thick pink curve) compared with published fractionation curves for CaCO_3 –water. A and C
 204 denote aragonite and calcite, respectively. Bio and Inorg denote biogenic carbonates and inorganic
 205 precipitation experiments. Our $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ isotope fractionation curve is consistent with other studies.
 206 (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web
 207 version of this article).

208

209 4. DISCUSSION

210 4.1. Mineralogy and molarity

211 Calcite and aragonite are two common carbonate minerals that are used in paleoclimate
 212 and paleo-environment reconstruction (e.g., in speleothems, foraminifera, mollusk shells, and lake
 213 deposits). Often, calcite and aragonite co-occur in one sample (e.g., in speleothems; Holmgren et
 214 al., 2003; Voarintsoa et al., 2017). In such cases, the difference in $^{18}\alpha$ between the two polymorphs
 215 (Kim et al., 2007b) has to be accounted for in the aragonite $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ to conform with the calcite values
 216 and to avoid bias in the interpretation of the data. The polymorph independence of the fractionation
 217 slope θ observed in this study (Table 3, Figure 4c) suggest that regardless of whether a sample is
 218 composed of pure calcite (e.g., foraminifera), aragonite (e.g., many mollusk shells), or a mixture
 219 of both (e.g., some speleothems or lake deposits), it should not pose further complications when

220 calculating $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ as part of the interpretation of carbonate triple oxygen isotopes data to
221 reconstruct $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in their parent water. This polymorph independence of θ has been observed
222 also in theoretical models (Guo and Zhou, 2019). The modeled absolute values of $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$
223 (0.5256 and 0.5257, respectively, for calcite and aragonite at 25°C) are higher than our
224 experimental $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ values (0.5228 and 0.5226, respectively for calcite and aragonite at
225 27°C), with the difference likely reflecting, at least in part, the fractionation between CaCO_3 and
226 CO_2 extracted from it (see below).

227 We also found that initial Mg:Ca ratio and DIC concentration (5mM and 25mM, at 27°C) do
228 not significantly affect θ and the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values (Figures 4a; Table 3). The initial solution
229 concentration and the Mg:Ca ratio used in this study are not far from those in natural systems, such
230 as cave drip water (between 0 and 1.5; e.g., Matthey et al., 2010; Oster et al., 2012) and seawater
231 (around 5; e.g., Ligi et al., 2013, and references therein). Our results are therefore relevant for
232 natural samples, but as discussed below, caution should be taken as to the higher temperature data,
233 as these may be influenced by various kinetic isotopic effects such as fast degassing and fast
234 precipitation rates. It appears, therefore, that $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in carbonates is less sensitive than $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ to
235 geochemical parameters, simplifying its interpretation as a proxy for reconstructing paleo-
236 hydrological conditions.

237

238 **4.2. Temperature dependence of $^{17}\alpha$**

239 It has been long known, and also observed in this current study, that the ^{18}O isotopic
240 fractionation factor between carbonate and water is temperature dependent; it decreases while
241 temperature increases. Although there are variations among ^{18}O thermometer calibrations (e.g.,
242 Figure 2), this relationship has enabled carbonate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ to be used as a tool for reconstructing paleo-

243 temperatures (e.g., Urey, 1947; Emiliani, 1966). The general consistency of the $^{18}\alpha$ obtained from
244 our samples with common ^{18}O thermometer calibrations allows us to examine $^{17}\alpha$ between
245 carbonate and its parent water, and what controls $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in CaCO_3 .

246 The difference in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ between $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ and water in our experiments is similar at 10°C
247 and 35°C (-222 ± 14 and -227 ± 9 per meg), and is somewhat higher at 27°C (-207 ± 12 per meg).
248 Figure 3 compares these observed values (as well the corresponding values for carbonate-water)
249 to those predicted by model simulations (Hayles et al., 2018; Guo and Zhou, 2019). The observed
250 15 per meg difference between 10 and 27°C is consistent with the results of the models, and it
251 approximately reflects the temperature dependence of $^{18}\alpha$, as the change in θ is small. The value
252 at 35°C , however, deviates from the modeled trend. There is no analytical reason to reject the set
253 of experiments at 35°C , but it is possible that kinetic isotope effects have played a significant role.
254 Laboratory precipitation experiments are inherently fast, leading to potential kinetic isotope effect
255 due to fast CO_2 degassing and fast mineral growth (e.g., Gabitov et al., 2012), which are likely to
256 be more pronounced in our high temperature experiments. In these experiments, first precipitates
257 were observed after 15–30 minutes. This time is shorter than needed to reach equilibrium between
258 DIC and CO_2 in air (about 2 hours; Guo and Zhou, 2019) and also for the DIC to reach isotopic
259 equilibrium at the experimental temperature, through exchange with water, which is expected to
260 be even slower (Guo and Zhou, 2019). The non-equilibrium conditions, stemming from a
261 combination of processes, may lead to the observed deviations at 35°C .

262

263 **Figure 3:** The difference in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ between X (= $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ or CaCO_3) and water in our
 264 experiments (data points) compared to the theoretical models (lines) of Hayles et al. (2018) and
 265 Guo and Zhou (2019). CaCO_3 observed values are calculated from the measured $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ using
 266 the acid digestion fractionation derived from either Wostbrock et al. (2020) or Guo et al. (2009),
 267 as in Table 2. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is
 268 referred to the web version of this article).

269

270 To calculate $^{17}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ we must convert our measured $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ data to that of carbonate.

271 This requires knowing the ^{17}O fractionation factor for the acid digestion of CaCO_3 to CO_2 ($^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$).

272 There are currently no accepted values for $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ for either calcite or aragonite, as opposed to

273 $^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ of 1.01025 (Kim et al., 2015) and 1.01063 (Kim et al., 2007a) for these minerals,

274 respectively. Wostbrock et al. (2020) suggest an experimental value for $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ in calcite reacted at

275 25°C. However, knowing that there is a significant difference in $^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ between calcite and

276 aragonite, it is likely that $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ values also differ between the two polymorphs. As our samples

277 are composed of calcite, aragonite, and mixtures of both (Figure 1), we cannot use the calcite $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$

278 of Wostbrock et al. (2020) to directly convert our CO_{2-carb} data to carbonate values. Instead, we
279 assume that the fractionation slope for the phosphoric acid digestion at 25°C, θ_{acid} ($= \ln^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}} /$
280 $\ln^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$), is the same for both calcite and aragonite, so that $^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ and $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ vary together with
281 polymorph. Based on this assumption, we derive the ^{17}O fractionation factor for the acid digestion
282 ($^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$) for both minerals using the accepted $^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ and θ_{acid} (see below).

283 There are two suggested values for the relationship between $^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ and $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ for calcite
284 reacted at 25°C. A θ_{acid} value of 0.5230 was obtained via fluorination of CaCO₃ (Wostbrock et al.,
285 2020), and a value of 0.5281 was determined by transition state theory modeling (Guo et al., 2009).
286 As we do not know *a priori* which of these θ_{acid} values (if any) is correct, we examine our data in
287 the context of both θ_{acid} values. We use θ_{acid} together with the accepted ^{18}O acid fractionations
288 factors for calcite and aragonite (Kim et al., 2007a; 2015), to calculate $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ (Table 2). Using the
289 θ_{acid} of 0.5230 from Wostbrock et al. (2020), we obtained $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ values of 1.00535 and 1.00555
290 for calcite and aragonite, respectively. Using the θ_{acid} of 0.5281 of Guo et al. (2009), we obtained
291 respective $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}}$ values of 1.00540 and 1.00560. Samples of mixed polymorphs were then
292 calculated as: $^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid}} = \% \text{calcite} \times ^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid-calcite}} + \% \text{aragonite} \times ^{17}\alpha_{\text{acid-aragonite}}$. The resulting CaCO₃
293 $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ values are given in Table 2, from which we can calculate the fractionation between CaCO₃
294 and H₂O using both θ_{acid} values (Table 3).

295

296 **4.3. The fractionation slope $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$**

297 Using the $^{17}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ and $^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ above, we calculated $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ (Table 3, Figure
298 4). The advantage of using $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ rather than directly $^{17}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ is that it normalizes
299 differences that are known to occur in $^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ among different types of carbonates (e.g.,
300 biogenic versus laboratory precipitated carbonates; Figure 2). Using $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$, it is possible to

301 rely on the vast literature data of $^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ to calculate $^{17}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ for different cases. Table 3
 302 gives values of $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ using the two different θ_{acid} values noted above, as well as the
 303 $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ which is based directly on the measured CO_2 extracted from carbonate, without
 304 accounting for the acid digestion fractionation.

305
 306 **Figure 4:** Fractionation slope in the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system presented in box-and-whisker plots that
 307 show outlier points (little dot) as a function of (a) molarity (initial concentration of the solution for
 308 the 27°C experiments), (b) temperature, and (c) mineralogy. Values calculated using θ_{acid} of 0.5230
 309 or 0.5281 are shown in grey and orange, respectively. Calculated $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values using the model
 310 of Hayles et al. (2018) at 10, 27, and 35°C are shown in blue in Figure 4b. Details are given in
 311 Table 3. The boxes show the interquartile range, calculated including the samples' median
 312 (horizontal line inside the box). The horizontal lines that mark off the box at the lower and upper
 313 hinge are the 25th and the 75th percentiles, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to
 314 color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).
 315

316 The results indicate that under laboratory precipitation conditions between 10 and 35°C,
 317 $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ does not vary with polymorph, meaning that it is the same for our calcite and aragonite
 318 samples (Figure 4c), consistent with model predictions (Guo and Zhou, 2019). In terms of the
 319 effect of temperature, for both polymorphs $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ obtained at 10°C and 27°C are
 320 indistinguishable (0.5228 and 0.5225, respectively, using θ_{acid} of 0.5230), but those at 35°C are
 321 lower (0.5215; Table 3).

322 Modeling studies predict a positive temperature dependence of ~ 0.00001 change in
323 $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ for a change in 1°C (Cao and Liu, 2011; Hayles et al., 2018; Guo and Zhou, 2019). For
324 the temperature range of 25°C in our experiments this would result in a range of $0.0002\text{-}0.0003$
325 around the mean $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ value, which is within our analytical uncertainty. We found a similarly
326 negligible trend between 10 and 27°C , but our lower $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ value at 35°C show a relatively
327 steep negative shift (a decrease of ~ 0.001 between 27 and 35°C) which is inconsistent with the
328 models (Figure 4b). As discussed above for the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ difference between $\text{CO}_2\text{-carb}$ and water (see
329 Section 4.2), this lower $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ value in the 35°C experiments could result from a combination
330 of kinetic effects that require further investigation.

331 Irrespective of the temperature trend, the absolute $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values in recent models
332 (Hayles et al., 2018; Guo and Zhou, 2019) are higher than our experimental data. The choice of
333 θ_{acid} , however, can strongly influence the resulting experimental $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values. Given the large
334 uncertainty in θ_{acid} , we examine $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ using both available values. The $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values
335 calculated using the θ_{acid} of Wostbrock et al. (2020) are close to our $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ (e.g.,
336 0.5227 ± 0.0003 for samples grown at 27°C), due to the similar value of θ_{acid} (0.5230). This is lower
337 than the values predicted by the theoretical models ($0.5256\text{-}0.5258$ for calcite grown at 25°C ;
338 Hayles et al., 2018; Guo and Zhou., 2019) and a preliminary experimental $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ of 0.5252 for
339 calcite grown at 30°C (Gibbons et al., 2017). However, when using the θ_{acid} of Guo et al. (2009)
340 the $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values obtained are even lower, 0.5207 ± 0.0003 (for the 27°C samples). Although
341 the model of Guo and Zhou (2019) predicts no significant difference between $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ for calcite
342 and aragonite, as we observed (Table 3), the absolute $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values suggested by this model
343 are inconsistent with our experimental results, for either one of the available values of θ_{acid} . The

344 consistency between the modeled $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values and those directly measured by Gibbons et al.
345 (2017), together with the inconsistency with our data that is based on measuring $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$,
346 suggest that both available values for θ_{acid} are likely wrong.

347 Passey et al. (2014) measured $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ in biogenic calcite and aragonite, comprising of
348 an oyster shell, a coral, and eggshells that grew at temperatures of 24, 26 and 39°C. (Note that they
349 report the fractionation slope as λ , rather than θ , to indicate that the fractionations are associated
350 with a combination of several processes. For simplicity, we use the symbol θ for the fractionation
351 slope either in the case of a single equilibrium process or for a combination of processes). They
352 observed a mean $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ value of 0.5245 ± 0.0002 that is higher than our observed value. The
353 coral sample deviated in both $^{17}\alpha$ and $^{18}\alpha$, likely reflecting the vital effect that is often observed
354 in corals, but the fractionation slope of the coral was the same as that for oyster and eggshells,
355 showing lack of trend with either temperature or polymorph.

356 The observed inter-laboratory difference in the mean $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ value may be associated
357 with systematic errors related to the different sample preparation method used in both laboratories.
358 It is important to note that there is also a difference of ~ 50 per meg in $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ of standards
359 measured in both laboratories (Barkan et al., 2019). If this difference in standards is accounted for
360 in the data of Passey et al. (2014), the $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ obtained from these data is 0.5231, much closer
361 to the value we obtain here. Preliminary data from aragonitic freshwater mollusks measured in our
362 laboratory also yield a $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ value of 0.5231 ± 0.0003 (Affek et al., 2019). This value is
363 consistent with the scaled value of Passey et al. (2014) and is also within error from the values
364 obtained here from laboratory precipitation at 10 and 27°C (where we do not suspect dis-
365 equilibrium).

366 The different analytical procedure and the uncertainty in θ_{acid} discussed above may explain
367 discrepancies in the absolute $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ values among laboratories, or a difference between
368 measured $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ and modeled of $\theta_{\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$. These cannot explain, however, a different trend
369 with temperature. Although models also include uncertainty, the lack of temperature trend in the
370 Passey et al. data set is consistent with the very weak trend predicted by the models. Whereas our
371 10 and 27°C data also shows no trend, the 35°C data is offset in both $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ and $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$. The
372 eggshell calcite in Passey et al. grew at 39°C but their $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ is similar to the lower
373 temperature samples, suggesting that it is probably not the temperature itself that leads to our lower
374 $\theta_{\text{CO}_2\text{carb-H}_2\text{O}}$ value at 35°C. Instead, the offset may be related to differences between laboratory
375 precipitation and biogenic mineral growth or to specific differences between our high temperature
376 experiments and the lower temperatures, such as the kinetic effects noted above. Further
377 measurements at a range of temperatures for both biogenic carbonates and laboratory precipitation
378 using a variety of methods, as well as experiments focusing specifically on the effect of growth
379 rates and of degassing, may help resolve these discrepancies.

380

381 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

382 Results from this experimental study allow us to determine the triple oxygen isotope
383 fractionations in the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system. We found that the fractionation slope $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ is: (1)
384 polymorph independent, i.e., we observe no significant difference between calcite, aragonite, and
385 their mixture; (2) indistinguishable at temperatures of 10 and 27°C but possibly slightly lower at
386 35°C (the lower value may be associated with kinetic effects related to the fast precipitation
387 observed in these experiments); and (3) independent of the molarity of the precipitating solution.
388 These are also reflected in the $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ values of the carbonates, that seem to be insensitive to a

389 range of geochemical parameters. The triple oxygen isotopes in carbonates could therefore be a
390 robust novel proxy for $^{17}\text{O}_{\text{excess}}$ in parent water and thus used to understand past hydrological
391 processes.

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394

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557

558 **Table 1:** Summary of the experimental conditions and ^{18}O data for the inorganically precipitated
 559 calcite and aragonite and their corresponding water at 10, 27, and 35°C.
 560

T °C	Molarity	Samples ^a	Mg:Ca	%A ^b	pH _i	pH _f	$\delta^{18}_{\text{CaCO}_3}$	$\delta^{18}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3-\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$1000\ln^{18}\alpha_{\text{CaCO}_3-\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
10 °C ^c	25mM	1	0	0	7.60	6.8	34.265	1.134	1.03309	32.55
	25mM	2	3	88	7.60	7.43	33.949	0.913	1.03301	32.47
	25mM	3	4	99	7.60	7.72	33.665	0.799	1.03284	32.31
	25mM	4	5	100	7.67	7.57	33.784	1.210	1.03254	32.02
27 °C ^d	25mM	5	0	0	7.14	6.31	31.009	1.493	1.02947	29.05
	25mM	6	4	97	7.14	6.89	30.612	1.456	1.02911	28.70
35 °C ^e	25mM	7	0	0	6.87	6.36	27.806	0.110	1.02769	27.32
	25mM	8	1	8	7.08	6.75	27.800	0.229	1.02756	27.19
	25mM	9	2	79	7.32	6.97	27.826	0.249	1.02757	27.20
27 °C ^d	5mM	10	0	4	5.89	5.85	28.453	0.400	1.02804	27.66
	5mM	11	1	37	6.02	6.01	28.990	0.380	1.02860	28.20
	5mM	12	2	100	6.42	6.64	29.270	0.493	1.02876	28.36

561
 562 ^a All samples were prepared without initial CO₂ bubbling, and they were precipitated via passive CO₂
 563 degassing. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{CaCO}_3}$ was calculated using the acid fractionation of 1.01025 (Kim et al., 2015) and
 564 1.01063 (Kim et al., 2007b) for calcite and aragonite, respectively, and using the following equation for
 565 samples of mixed polymorphs: $^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid}} = \% \text{calcite} \times ^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid-calcite}} + \% \text{aragonite} \times ^{18}\alpha_{\text{acid-aragonite}}$. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data is
 566 given versus VSMOW.
 567 ^b Percent aragonite, determined by XRD.
 568 ^c Covered flask placed in an incubator with shaking platform.
 569 ^d Covered flask placed in an incubator without shaking.
 570 ^e Covered flask placed in a thermally controlled water bath, without shaking.

571
 572

573 **Table 2:** Summary of the triple oxygen isotopic composition of the CaCO₃ precipitates and their
574 corresponding water. The units are ‰ for both δ¹⁷O and δ¹⁸O and per meg for ¹⁷O_{excess}.
575

Sample	CO ₂ -carb			CO ₂ eq. with H ₂ O		CaCO ₃ (W&al) ^a			CaCO ₃ (G&al) ^a			H ₂ O ^b		
	δ ¹⁷ O	δ ¹⁸ O	¹⁷ O _{excess}	δ ¹⁷ O	δ ¹⁸ O	δ ¹⁷ O	δ ¹⁸ O	¹⁷ O _{excess}	δ ¹⁷ O	δ ¹⁸ O	¹⁷ O _{excess}	δ ¹⁷ O	δ ¹⁸ O	¹⁷ O _{excess}
1	23.237	44.866	-202	21.886	42.217	17.794	34.265	-151	17.741	34.265	-203	0.618	1.134	20
2	23.238	44.892	-214	21.762	41.987	17.619	33.949	-162	17.565	33.949	-216	0.497	0.913	15
3	23.133	44.649	-194	21.693	41.867	17.492	33.665	-141	17.437	33.665	-195	0.430	0.799	9
4	23.176	44.774	-215	21.927	42.296	17.534	33.785	-162	17.479	33.785	-216	0.659	1.210	20
5	21.537	41.577	-200	22.074	42.591	16.104	31.009	-149	16.051	31.009	-201	0.803	1.493	15
6	21.517	41.555	-208	22.040	42.551	15.890	30.612	-156	15.835	30.612	-210	0.769	1.456	1
7	19.863	38.341	-197	21.336	41.151	14.438	27.806	-146	14.385	27.806	-198	0.080	0.110	22
8	19.879	38.367	-195	21.419	41.274	14.438	27.800	-144	14.385	27.800	-196	0.162	0.229	41
9	20.032	38.670	-198	21.416	41.296	14.449	27.826	-146	14.395	27.826	-200	0.158	0.249	27
10	20.223	39.012	-185	21.471	41.452	14.788	28.453	-134	14.735	28.453	-186	0.212	0.400	1
11	20.555	39.683	-201	21.467	41.432	15.051	28.990	-150	14.998	28.990	-202	0.209	0.380	8
12	20.845	40.211	-185	21.552	41.549	15.215	29.270	-133	15.160	29.270	-187	0.291	0.493	31

576
577 ^a The δ¹⁸O values of the carbonates were obtained after applying the phosphoric acid
578 fractionation factors ¹⁸α=1.01025 and ¹⁸α =1.01063 (Kim et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2007a) for
579 calcite and aragonite, respectively. The δ¹⁷O values of the carbonates were calculated using the
580 phosphoric acid fractionation slope (θ_{acid} = ln¹⁷α/ln¹⁸α) of 0.5230 (Wostbrock et al. 2020;
581 W&al), and 0.5281 (Guo et al., 2009; G&al), and the above phosphoric acid fractionation factors
582 ¹⁸α for calcite and aragonite.
583 ^b The δ¹⁸O and δ¹⁷O values of the water were derived by applying the CO₂–H₂O equilibrium
584 fractionation factors ¹⁸α_{H₂O–CO₂} = 1.041036±0.00008 and ¹⁷α_{H₂O–CO₂} = 1.021254±0.00004 (Barkan
585 and Luz, 2012).
586

587 **Table 3:** Summary of the fractionation factors ($^{17}\alpha$ and $^{18}\alpha$) and their corresponding fractionation
 588 slope, calculated from (1) CO₂ extracted from CaCO₃ (CO_{2-carb}) and H₂O, (2) CaCO₃ and H₂O
 589 using $\theta_{\text{acid}} = 0.5230$ (Wostbrock et al. 2020), and (3) CaCO₃ and H₂O using $\theta_{\text{acid}} = 0.5281$ (Guo et
 590 al., 2009).
 591

T °C	Sample ^a	%A ^c	1. CO _{2-carb} – water			2. Carbonate–water ($\theta=0.5230$)			3. Carbonate–water ($\theta=0.5281$)		
			$^{17}\alpha$	$^{18}\alpha$	θ	$^{17}\alpha$	$^{18}\alpha$	θ	$^{17}\alpha$	$^{18}\alpha$	θ
10 °C	1	0	1.02260	1.04368	0.5228	1.01717	1.03309	0.5228	1.01711	1.03309	0.5212
	2	88	1.02273	1.04394	0.5227	1.01711	1.03301	0.5226	1.01706	1.03301	0.5209
	3	99	1.02269	1.04382	0.5233	1.01705	1.03284	0.5234	1.01700	1.03284	0.5217
	4	100	1.02250	1.04351	0.5225	1.01686	1.03254	0.5223	1.01681	1.03254	0.5207
	Avg.		1.02263	1.04374	0.5228	1.01705	1.03287	0.5228	1.01700	1.03287	0.5211
	$\pm SE^*t$		<i>0.00010</i>	<i>0.00018</i>	<i>0.0003</i>	<i>0.00013</i>	<i>0.00025</i>	<i>0.0005</i>	<i>0.00013</i>	<i>0.00025</i>	<i>0.0005</i>
27 °C	5	0	1.02072	1.04002	0.5225	1.01529	1.02947	0.5224	1.01524	1.02947	0.5206
	6	97	1.02073	1.04004	0.5227	1.01511	1.02911	0.5225	1.01506	1.02911	0.5207
	Avg.		1.02072	1.04003	0.5226	1.01520	1.02929	0.5225	1.01515	1.02929	0.5207
	$\pm SE^*t$		<i>0.00001</i>	<i>0.00001</i>	<i>0.0001</i>	<i>0.00013</i>	<i>0.00025</i>	<i>0.0001</i>	<i>0.00013</i>	<i>0.00025</i>	<i>0.0001</i>
	10 ^b	4	1.02001	1.03860	0.5231	1.01457	1.02804	0.5231	1.01452	1.02804	0.5213
	11 ^b	37	1.02034	1.03929	0.5226	1.01484	1.02860	0.5224	1.01479	1.02860	0.5206
	12 ^b	100	1.02055	1.03970	0.5224	1.01492	1.02876	0.5222	1.01487	1.02876	0.5204
	Avg.		1.02030	1.03919	0.5227	1.01478	1.02847	0.5225	1.01472	1.02847	0.5207
	$\pm SE^*t$		<i>0.00027</i>	<i>0.00056</i>	<i>0.0004</i>	<i>0.00018</i>	<i>0.00038</i>	<i>0.0005</i>	<i>0.00018</i>	<i>0.00038</i>	<i>0.0005</i>
	35 °C	7	0	1.01978	1.03823	0.5222	1.01436	1.02769	0.5218	1.01431	1.02769
8	8	1.01971	1.03813	0.5217	1.01427	1.02756	0.5212	1.01422	1.02756	0.5193	
9	79	1.01987	1.03841	0.5220	1.01429	1.02757	0.5216	1.01423	1.02757	0.5197	
Avg.		1.01979	1.03826	0.5220	1.01431	1.02761	0.5215	1.01425	1.02761	0.5197	
$\pm SE^*t$		<i>0.00008</i>	<i>0.00014</i>	<i>0.0002</i>	<i>0.00005</i>	<i>0.00007</i>	<i>0.0003</i>	<i>0.00004</i>	<i>0.00007</i>	<i>0.0003</i>	

592
 593 ^a See details for each sample in Tables 1 and 2. ^b Samples precipitated at 27°C with a lower
 594 molarity (5mM). ^c Percent aragonite.
 595

596

597 **Figure captions:**

598

599 **Figure 1:** Scatter plot showing the distribution of CaCO₃ polymorphs precipitated in this study, as
600 a function of Mg:Ca ratio and temperature (°C), compared to the data of Morse et al. (1997). The
601 proportion of each mineral in each sample was determined via XRD, and is depicted in the blue /
602 green partitioning of the symbol. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend,
603 the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

604

605 **Figure 2:** The ¹⁸O/¹⁶O isotopic fractionation curve between CaCO₃ and H₂O calculated in this
606 study (thick pink curve) compared with published fractionation curves for CaCO₃–water. A and C
607 denote aragonite and calcite, respectively. Bio and Inorg denote biogenic carbonates and inorganic
608 precipitation experiments. Our ¹⁸O/¹⁶O isotope fractionation curve is consistent with other studies.
609 (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web
610 version of this article).

611

612 **Figure 3:** The difference in ¹⁷O_{excess} between X (= CO_{2-carb} or CaCO₃) and water in our
613 experiments (data points) compared to the theoretical models (lines) of Hayles et al. (2018) and
614 Guo and Zhou (2019). In the data points, CaCO₃ values are calculated from the measured
615 CO_{2-carb} using the acid digestion fractionation derived from either Wostbrock et al. (2020) or Guo
616 et al. (2009), as in Table 2. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the
617 reader is referred to the web version of this article).

618

619 **Figure 4:** Fractionation slope in the $\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system presented in box-and-whisker plots that
620 show outlier points (little dot) as a function of (a) molarity (initial concentration of the solution for
621 the 27 °C experiments), (b) temperature, and (c) mineralogy. Values calculated using θ_{acid} of
622 0.5230 or 0.5281 are shown in grey and orange, respectively. Calculated $\theta_{\text{CaCO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}}$ values using
623 the model of Hayles et al. (2018) at 10, 27, and 35°C are shown in blue in Figure 4b. Details are
624 given in Table 3. The boxes show the interquartile range, calculated including the samples' median
625 (horizontal line inside the box). The horizontal lines that mark off the box at the lower and upper
626 hinge are the 25th and the 75th percentiles, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to
627 color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

628